

Roadside Reflection of Nigeria's Declining Vultures: A study across Five Contiguous States (Plateau, Kaduna, Nasarawa, Benue, and Enugu)

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Abstract

Globally, vultures and other raptors are facing a critical population crisis, with forecasts suggesting that up to 40% of species may become extinct within the next 30 years. This alarming declining trend is particularly pronounced in Africa, where vulture populations have drastically declined, with many species experiencing severe reductions or even local extinctions. In Nigeria, this decline is especially severe, with historical records indicating once-abundant vulture populations now reduced to only a few remaining species. This study aimed to evaluate the current status of vultures and other raptors across five contiguous states in Nigeria: Plateau, Kaduna, Nasarawa, Benue, and Enugu. The survey was conducted from January 28 to February 2, 2019, using an open Hillux traveling at 45 km/hour. Observations were made by two researchers from an opened truck, who recorded the number of raptors encountered and their locations at various times of the day. Data analysis was done using a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) in R to assess species abundance and compare raptor abundance across the states. The results were visualised using bar charts. A total of 217 raptors were sighted, with Yellow-billed Kites (*Milvus aegyptius*) being the most numerous, followed by Common kestrels (*Falco tinnunculus*). Vultures were significantly less abundant, with only three Palm-nut Vultures (*Gypobierax angolensis*) and two Hooded Vultures (*Necrosyrtes monachus*) recorded. This stark contrast highlights the severe decline in vulture populations in Nigeria, underlining the urgent need for conservation actions. The findings emphasise the urgent need for targeted conservation efforts to protect vultures and other raptors. Recommendations include, increasing public awareness, implementing protective legislation, and improving habitat management. Engaging local communities and enforcing laws against illegal hunting and trade in avian fauna are essential for preserving Nigeria's raptor populations and preventing further declines.

Keywords: *Raptors, Vultures, Species decline, Nigeria, Conservation, Road transect survey, Hooded vulture, Palmnut vulture, Population assessment, Avian scavengers, Threats to wildlife, Plateau state, Kaduna state, Nasarawa state, Benue state, Enugu state.*

Suggested citation: Williams, M.M., Yilgwan, P.L., Junior, M.F., Adendem, M.N., Pam, E.D., & Yiljika, J.D. (2024). Roadside Reflection of Nigeria's Declining Vultures: A study across Five Contiguous States (Plateau, Kaduna, Nasarawa, Benue, and Enugu). *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 1(4), 15-22. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2024.1(4).02

Introduction

The global rate of species decline is accelerating, with a prediction that 40% of species will be extinct within 30 years (Kosch 2022). Even with this type of alarm calls, Vultures' population has been decreasing drastically in Africa (Oluwaseun 2017), with a higher than initially imagined decline in West Africa (Thiollay 2006). Nigeria has the worst scenario of vulture decline as many communities already faced local extinction of vultures which used to be rampant (Nosazogie et al., 2018; Manja et al. 2021). A similar trend of population decline is observed among other raptors, most of which are sinking in to extinction without detection, because of insufficient monitoring data in most African countries.

Nigeria was home to seven vulture species: White-headed Vulture (*Trigonoceps occipitalis*), Palm-nut Vulture (*Gypobierax angolensis*), Hooded Vulture (*Necrosyrtes monachus*), African White-backed Vulture (*Gyps africanus*), Lappet-faced Vulture (*Torgos tracheliotos*), Egyptian Vulture (*Neophron percnopterus*), Rüppell's Griffon Vulture (*Gyps rueppelli*), (Borrow & Demey, 2013). Most of these vulture species found in Nigeria are endangered (Soneye, 2023). They are in severe threat as their population is nearing collapse (Agbana 2023). Road transect across some Northern states of Nigeria revealed the extreme extent of vulture decline as only one Hooded vulture was found (Ringim et al. 2022). This is against the findings of many vultures in Sokoto and other Northern Nigerian states in the 70s, 80s and early 90s (Mundy 1992). Based on interviews with older people, numerous vultures were sighted even hanging by the road, hovering visibly in the sky, around slaughter houses and dump sites in towns and villages and in the outskirts of the town back then in 1970s and 80s, and this goes in line with the research report that, vultures were a common sight in the environment, because in only one location, 660 vultures were reportedly sighted foraging in Yankari National park (Green 1989). In 2007, when Tende visited the same park, 22 vultures were found, indicating a decline when compared with the report of Green (Tende & Ottoson, 2007). Today, five of the seven species have extinct, only hooded and palmnut vultures seen (Ujorha, 2012) with their population increasingly reducing and causing their rare sightings in few communities of Nigeria. The decline in vulture population is glaring in some parts of Nigeria. (Tende, 2007; Dunn 2010; Ogada & Buij, 2013).

The rapid decline of vulture population in Nigeria is due to numerous factors that range from habitat lose, illegal hunting, trades in their parts for juju, and traditional believes which make people to label them as evil (Ogada, et al. 2015). Traditional belief system is found to be the major cause of vulture decline in Nigeria (Williams et al. 2021; Awoyemi et al., 2021). Threats like food shortages, persecution, electrocution, and heavy metals poisoning (especially lead) also constitute sources of danger to avian scavengers (Bernyetal, 2015). Massive trades in vulture parts also attributes to vulture's population decline, as approximately 500 tones are trafficked monthly for use in traditional medicine (Oluwaseun, 2017). Vultures are no longer seen everywhere as before, only few can be seen in few locations across different states of Nigeria, this is largely because of the decline in their population. Though few of the vultures still exist in some communities in the country, the vultures are no longer seen as rampant as they were. This study was carried to ascertain the number of vultures which can be sighted during a road count in any of the five states in Nigeria.

Aim of the Study

The aim of the study was to determine the number of vultures and other raptors that could be sighted during a road count across five states (Plateau, Kaduna, Nasarawa, Benue and Enugu states) of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the abundance of different species of vultures sighted during a road count from North-central to South-Eastern Nigeria.
2. To ascertain the differences in abundance of raptors across five states of Nigeria.

Methodology

Description of Study Sites

The study conducted road transect surveys across five contiguous states in Nigeria: Plateau, Kaduna, Nasarawa, Benue, and Enugu, each with distinct geographical and climatic characteristics. Kaduna State (approximately 10.3°N, 7.4°E) has a unique landscape with a mix of savannah and forested areas. The northern part is predominantly savannah, while the southern regions transition into more forested environments. Kaduna experiences a tropical climate with a pronounced wet season from April to October and a dry season from November to March. Annual rainfall ranges between 1,200 mm and 1,400 mm. The state is situated in the Northern Guinea Savanna zone, merging into the Sudan Savanna to the north. Plateau State (approximately 9.3°N, 9.5°E) is distinguished by its highland plateau, characterized by montane grasslands, savannah, and scattered woodlands. The state's high altitude imparts a temperate climate with cooler temperatures compared to other Nigerian regions. The rainfall ranges from 1,000 mm to 1,400 mm, with a shorter wet season and a longer dry period. The Jos Plateau offers a unique ecoregion due to its elevation, contributing to its distinct vegetation and climate. Nasarawa State (approximately 8.5°N, 8.5°E) features a landscape of mixed savannah and forested areas. The state's predominantly savannah environment is less forested compared to the southern states. Nasarawa experiences a tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons. Rainfall varies between 1,000 mm and 1,200 mm, with the wet season running from April to October and the dry season from November to March. The state is located in the Northern Guinea Savanna zone, similar to Kaduna but with a more consistent savannah landscape.

Benue State (approximately 7.2°N, 9.7°E) is known for its fertile lands and lush vegetation, including riverine forests and dense savannah. The state's proximity to the Benue River contributes to its rich biodiversity. Benue enjoys a tropical climate with high annual rainfall, ranging from 1,500 mm to 2,000 mm. The rainy season extends from March to October, while the dry season lasts from November to February. Benue is situated in the Southern Guinea Savanna zone, with a more humid and verdant environment compared to the northern states. Finally, Enugu State (approximately 6.4°N, 7.5°E) features tropical rainforest in its southern parts and transitional forests and savannah in the north. Known for its dense vegetation and high biodiversity, Enugu experiences a tropical rainforest climate with significant annual rainfall between 1,500 mm and 2,000 mm. The wet season runs from March to October, and the dry season from November to February. Enugu lies within the Rainforest zone of Nigeria, providing a rich habitat that contrasts with the more arid northern states. The variation in vegetation and climatic conditions across these states influences the distribution and abundance of vultures and other raptors, highlighting the importance of understanding these environmental factors in conservation efforts.

Figure 1. Map of Nigeria Showing the Transect Route and Points where Sightings of Vultures and Other Raptors were Made

Method of Data Collection

A road count of vultures and other raptors was conducted from 28th January, 2019 to 2nd February, 2019. The count started from Jos, plateau state (central Nigeria) to Enugu state (South-Eastern Nigeria), covering a distance of 561Km using an opened Hillux. The counts began around 6:00H to 17:00H at a speed of 45km/hour. The transect was across five states; Plateau, Kaduna, Nasarawa, Benue and Enugu. Two researchers sat behind an opened vehicle to observe birds. When a bird was seen the vehicle stopped for the researchers to make further observations and identification around the environment using pairs of binoculars and a Field Guide to the Birds of Western Africa (Borrow & Demey, 2013). All encountered raptors were recorded based on their location which was measured using global Positioning system (GPS) as the study was conducted (06:00-11:59), afternoon (12:00-15:59), and evening (16:00-17:00). In some parts of each state, we interacted with people on their views of raptors or vultures in a deliberate attempt to understand how human factors impact the raptors.

Methods of Data Analysis

The data was prepared in Microsoft Excel and was analysed using R-statistical package (R version 3.6.2, 2019). General Linear Model (GLM) in R was used. It was used to analyse research objectives one and two, determine the abundance of vultures across and also the difference in the abundance of raptors across the states. Bar charts were used for the visualisation of the result.

Results

Figure 2. Difference in the Abundance of Hooded Vultures and Palm-Nut Vultures as Observed during a Road Transect Study from North-Central to South-Eastern Nigeria

Figure 3. Difference in the Abundance of Raptors from North-Central Nigeria to South-Eastern

Discussion

The research was carried to investigate the abundance of vultures and other raptors across five states, from Northern Nigeria, to Eastern Nigeria using a road counting method. A total number of 217 raptors were encountered during the count. Among them, yellow-billed kite has the highest number of individuals (n=162), followed by Common kestrel; n=33, Fox kestrel; n=12, Lanner falcon (n=5), and the least were the vultures; Palm-nut vultures (n=3), and Hooded vulture (n=2).

In relation to fig 1, the survey encountered only two species of vultures (Hooded and Palm-nut vultures). This indicates that, other species of vultures have either extinct locally, or they are no longer sighted commonly. This result aligns to the report of (Ujorha, 2012), who postulated that, out of the seven vulture species Nigeria used to have, only two species are present, as others have gone in to extinction due to threats relating to killings, persecution and trades in their body parts across. More so, Ringim et al. (2022) found only one hooded vulture after a road counting of vultures across different Northern states of Nigeria. This indicates that, other species of vultures are hardly encountered except the hooded vulture and the hooded vultures are declining with unimaginable temporal speed. As in Fig. 2 hooded vultures are fewer in number across Nigeria; their population in the country is now estimated to be less than one thousand individuals of only two species. The Palm-nut vultures are found in riverine forests and are not too common as before. It is alarming to observe that the vulture population which used to be a common sight are now a very rare sight. In the 60s – 90s, one hardly moves from one village to the other without encountering one or more species of vultures, but today, it is very hard to even see two individual of the common species; hooded and Palmnut vultures. It is quite surprising to see that, a survey covering over 500 km led to the sighting of only five vultures of only two species, these two species are now the only survivors of the mass vulture extinction in Nigeria.

The encountering of only five individual vultures of only two species in this study, also depicts that, road count is not the best survey method for vultures now in Nigeria but point counts, as it can only be good when there are many vultures with good abundance. Most of the vultures due to threats and food scarcity, have relocated to locations with less threats and more food as observed by Tende and Ottosson (2008) who found that, most Hooded vultures in Yankari National park moved out of the park along with people, as the people relocated. Hooded vultures and other vultures have shown some relationship with human density, this is as a result of availability of food. Vultures can only be found in group and commonly at foraging sites such as abattoirs and dumping sites.

More so, as in fig. 3, other raptors showed decline in their abundance, especially Lanner falcons and fox kestrels. Yellow-billed kites were encountered in their high number (162). There were little threats against them, and they have conducive environment for reproduction. Benue, plateau and Enugu states tend to have the higher number of the raptors sighted during the road survey compares to Kaduna and Nasarawa states. The high number of taller trees, serve as conducive nesting sites for vultures. Cutting down these trees constituted existential threats to the already threatened species. It was observed that, though Nasarawa state had a lot of tall trees, not many raptors were recorded there, this could be as a result of threats related to hunting and destruction of nests as explained by some of the indigenous people, who were seen with catapults and other hunting materials. They said, most of the raptors couldn't allow them to rear chickens, and so they resolved to kill them. Some members of the states lamented that, there were moments that some people were killing Yellow-billed kites and selling to unsuspecting individuals as chicken meats. It was then thought that, that could also be a reason that despite high number of trees, raptors were not more abundant there.

Conclusion

The number of raptors encountered from Northern to South-Eastern Nigeria was quite low, with Vultures being the less abundant species. This was due to the decline in the population of the raptors across Nigeria. Threats against raptors in the country, is gradually extirpating them from the country's ecosystem. Most raptors are unnoticeably declining and taking the down curve towards extinction. Different communities in Nigeria, have different raptor species which they carelessly about or "protect" and other ones which they put so much hunting pressure on, and kill them in their numbers based on belief systems or quest for food (source of protein).

Recommendation

It is therefore, recommended that, more sensitisations be embarked upon in different communities across Nigeria to enlighten the people on how useful raptors and scavengers are to man alive, than dead. Quick and effective measures are required to be carried in protecting vultures, and in raising their population across the country. Implementation of laws protecting the endangered species of organisms such as the vultures, should be the priority of conservationists, government and nature enthusiasts. This will require the law makers to work in hand with the law enforcing agencies and community leaders and stakeholders.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge Biota Conservation Hub Foundation (BiotaCHF) for the logistical support which made this work a success. We appreciate our driver Mr Philibus Usman, who was patient and dedicated to the work. Much thanks to Andrew Manja for his field support throughout the days of the survey. We thank the communities in which the surveys were carried for their cooperation and understanding.

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